

WHITE PAPER

FORECASTING YOUR BEST PERFORMANCE:
MODELING COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE FROM SLEEP AND WORK PATTERNS
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ABSTRACT

This white paper* presents the derivation of a mathematical model, The Cognitive Model (*C Model*), designed to predict cognitive performance as a function of key factors including sleep duration, age, waking hours, work duration, and work break history. The model incorporates the effects of both nighttime sleep and daytime naps, with particular attention to the disproportionately large cognitive boost provided by short naps. Validation was performed by comparing the model's predictions against a broad range of published experimental and observational data. The results suggest potential applications in optimizing sleep and work schedules for individuals, enhancing productivity in educational and workspace settings, and informing the design of personalized health performance monitoring tools.

KEYWORDS:

sleep, cognition, productivity, fatigue, cognitive performance, sleep modeling, circadian rhythm, naps, work breaks, mathematical model, sleep deprivation, neuroscience

** At time of publication, this paper has not undergone formal peer review.*

INTRODUCTION

The paper is segmented into four sections,

- I. C MODEL DERIVATION – Description of the conceptual analog circuit and equation derivation. *The general reader can skip this section.*
- II. C MODEL INTEGRITY – The C Model's results are compared to a range of published and empirical data.
- III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS – C Model generated results using a number of common "real life" examples to illustrate the impact of sleep and work breaks on cognitive ability.
- IV. CONCLUSIONS

A brief explanation is useful to interpret the results.

- The C Model defines one's cognitive ability during waking hours as a function of sleep and work breaks. Cognitive ability is assumed to reflect one's potential to perform work.
- The C Model equations were derived using published data and the author's estimates where no data existed.
- The C Model assumes that after a fully restorative sleep we begin our day with maximum cognitive ability. This decreases with time as the day progresses and also as we focus on work. We recover these losses through a combination of work breaks and sleep. The concept is somewhat analogous to the operation of a computer. The device is recharged at night, and discharges during the day, the rate of discharge a function of cognitive work (i.e., concentration periods) and associated breaks (i.e., rest periods).
- The C Model incorporates the impact of sleep in the form of naps and core nighttime rest.

- Each individual also experiences circadian rhythms which affect cognitive ability during the day. For example, many people feel drowsy midway through their waking hours. These rhythms can modify the assumption that one is at maximum capacity at the beginning of the day. They also play an important role in one's ability to take a nap.
- To apply the C Model to individual cases requires the person's age along with the duration of their fully restorative sleep. Conversely, when modeling behavior for a group, the average age of the group members and their collective average sleep requirements is required.

I. C MODEL DERIVATION

Conceptual Analog Circuit

The discharge of a capacitor seems to mirror life experiences as it relates to cognitive ability. As a capacitor discharges, the voltage across the capacitor decays exponentially with time. Recharging the capacitor brings the voltage back to the original state. This is not unlike the process we go through daily, where we gradually deplete energy, both mentally and physically during waking hours (*i.e. discharge*), followed by a period of rest replenishment or sleep. Even during the day we require periodic breaks during prolonged intense mental concentration to “recharge our batteries.”

Figure 1.0 is a simplified analog circuit to illustrate the conceptual approach used in formulating algorithms associated with the actual Cognitive Model (C Model), where our cognitive ability at a specific point in time is represented by the relative voltage $V(t)$. It follows that cognitive work over a period of time ΔT ($\Delta = T_1 - T_2$) is assumed to be proportional to $\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (V(t) - k) dt$ where k is a constant.

A word of clarification as to why The Analog Circuit is described as conceptual as opposed to an equivalent circuit (*i.e. exact model*). As will become evident in the summary of equations, the functions are far more complex than those associated with simple RC circuits.

Figure 1 - Conceptual Analog Circuit

- C_0 = Represents the source of energy which powers the brain. C_0 is fully charged at birth to $V_0 = 1$ and slowly discharges during life.
- R_0 = Represents a constant load to the brain. Intuitively, this would include all biological functions common to conscious and non conscious states.
- C_1 = Stores energy to power the brain during waking hours. During a fully restorative sleep, C_1 is charged up to a maximum of the voltage on C_0 . During waking hours, C_1 discharges to provide energy necessary for T_w waking hours. Maximum voltage $VC_1 \leq VC_0$.
- R_1 = Resistance which affects time required to recharge C_1 when switched to sleep mode.
- R_2 = Represents the majority of the load to the brain during waking hours, assuming $R_3 \gg R_2$.
- R_3 = The resistance which in combination with R_4 , determines the discharge rate for C_2 .
- C_2 = Stores energy used for short term mental tasks. C_2 is discharged during these tasks and recharged back to a maximum voltage of that on C_1 during a fully restorative break.
- R_4 = Represents the load consuming energy while focusing on a task.
- SW_1 = Switch which establishes state of sleep or consciousness.
- SW_2 = A switch which during waking hours, establishes a state of mental concentration or relaxation (i.e. a break). When SW_1 is in the sleep position, SW_2 automatically defaults to the break position.

$$C_2 \lll C_1 \lll C_0 \qquad \frac{1}{R_1 C_1} \gg \frac{1}{R_0 C_0} \qquad \frac{1}{(R_1 + R_3) C_2} \gg \frac{1}{(R_1 + R_2) C_1}$$

$$VC_2 \leq VC_1 \leq VC_0$$

- VC_0 = Capacitor C_0 voltage
- VC_1 = Capacitor C_1 voltage
- VC_2 = Capacitor C_2 voltage
- R = Resistance
- C = Capacitance

Referring to Figure 1, The Analog Circuit incorporates three interconnected stages. Stage 1 contains capacitor C_0 which is assumed to be fully charged ($VC_0 = 1$) at the beginning of life and gradually discharges as life progresses. The rate of discharge is primarily determined by resistor R_0 . During sleep, SW_1 connects C_0 to capacitor C_1 . During a night of fully restorative sleep, capacitor C_1 is charged to the same voltage as VC_0 . Defining VC_1 as the voltage on capacitor C_1 , at the beginning of the day for a fully rested individual $VC_1 = VC_0$.

When an individual awakens, SW_1 moves to the “awake” position. Capacitor C_1 now becomes the source of energy during our waking period. The voltage on capacitor C_1 is gradually discharged until we revert back to the sleep mode. The sleep mode may be either a single night time of sleep (i.e. monophasic) or one (biphasic) or more (polyphasic) daytime naps augmented with a night time sleep. As will become evident, the restorative impact of a nap in recharging C_1 can be “non-linear” in that a short nap can provide a disproportionately higher level of restoration... it can provide far more impact than extending a night time sleep by the length of the nap.

In addition to being related to cognitive ability, VC_1 determines how tired we feel. When VC_1 diminishes to a level designated as V_s , we enter a condition known as zero sleep latency (a measure in minutes of how long it takes us to fall asleep). For a normal adult, bedtime ‘sleep latency’ is in the order of 15-20 minutes. For an individual who opts to take a short daytime nap of say 30 minutes, sleep latency would need to be 10-15 minutes or less to secure the benefit of the nap.

A second factor which very much impacts VC_1 and sleep latency is circadian rhythm, one’s 24 hour internal clock that runs in the background of one’s brain and cycles between sleepiness and alertness at regular intervals. Translating this to Figure 1, it means that VC_1 is modulated by one’s circadian rhythm, and needs to be accounted for in the study of naps where low sleep latency is essential.

What about the question of the amount of total daily sleep we require? This will

be presented in the subsequent section on derivation of general equations. Suffice to say that the derivation for the daily percentage sleep requirements is different for monophasic than biphasic/polyphasic sleep. The latter can yield equivalent restoration with a reduction in total sleep time.

Returning to Figure 1, consider one's waking hours where SW_1 is in the "awake" position. When we are not focusing on a mental task, SW_2 is in the "break" position. The voltage on C_2 is equal to that on capacitor C_1 or $VC_2 = VC_1$. However, when one begins working on a mental task SW_2 is in the "concentration" position. Now capacitor C_2 is the source of energy and begins to discharge until the individual takes a "break", where capacitor C_2 is either partially or totally recharged. If the break time is sufficient in length, capacitor C_2 is fully recharged to equal the voltage on C_1 or $VC_2 = VC_1$. If the break is insufficient in length, the individual will return to work with diminished capacity. Correspondingly, if the break exceeds the full recharge time, the excess time is nonproductive. As one would intuitively expect, the optimum break time and frequency is also very much age dependent. Mental task in this context implies actively requiring sustained concentration.

Summarizing, C_0 is the source of energy to power the brain. It is gradually discharged during one's lifespan. C_1 is the source of energy we use during waking hours. C_1 is charged during sleep to a voltage level equal to that of C_0 and then partially discharged during normal waking hours. In turn, C_1 is the source of energy to charge C_2 , which dictates our cognitive ability. More specifically, our cognitive ability during waking ours is proportional to the voltage of C_2 (VC_2) at that time less a constant designated by V_{th} [i.e. cognitive ability = $VC_2(t) - V_{th}$]. The latter reflects the idea that below some absolute value, (without external stimulation) we enter a state of 0 sleep latency. After continuous sleep deprivation, one eventually reaches a state of fatigue where useful cognitive work is not possible. This absolute threshold is assumed to be V_s , absent external stimulation.

During a time period of uninterrupted concentration ΔT , the amount of mental output or work is assumed to be proportional to $\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (VC_2(t) - Vth) dt$ where $T_1 - T_2 = \Delta T$ hours.

The C Model depicted in Figure 1 was derived through trial and error against the criteria that it behaved in a manner consistent with the basic phenomena we observe in life, i.e.,

1. We require a certain amount of daily sleep to function with maximum efficiency. The absolute amount of daily sleep required varies with the individual.
2. We require more sleep when we are young. The very young and very old require more sleep.
3. Sleep deprivation reduces cognitive ability.
4. Continuous sleep deprivation initially results in increasing fatigue where the period of time to fall asleep is effectively reduced to zero. Further continuous sleep deprivation ultimately results in the inability to do any useful mental tasks.
5. We need periodic breaks when conducting extended mental tasks.

Derivation of General Equations

Figure 2A - VC_0 as a Function of Age in Years

VC_0 = normalized voltage on capacitor C_0
 V_s = value where sleep latency approaches 0
 V_{th} = cognitive threshold voltage

Referring to Figure 2A, the relationship between age and the voltage (*normalized*) on capacitor C_0 is given by:

$$VC_0 = e^{-K_0 n} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where: n = age in years

K_0 = constant

$C_0 \gg \gg C_1$

Thus at birth $VC_0 = 1.0$ and this gradually depletes with age until VC_0 corresponds to a perpetual zero sleep latency state, including the impact of circadian rhythms.

First consider the case of monophasic sleep where an individual has a single, fully restorative night’s sleep. This cycle is shown in Figure 2B. During the night, Switch 1 (SW_1) is in the sleep position, Switch 2 is in the break position allowing Capacitor C_1 to be fully charged up to voltage VC_0 , the maximum possible. When the individual awakens, Switch 1 goes to the “awake” position. Capacitor C_1 is no longer

Figure 2B - Fully Restorative Monophasic Daily Sleep Cycle

receiving energy from C_0 , but is now gradually discharged over time until Switch 1 is returned to the sleep position. During waking hours the voltage on Capacitor C_1 is given by:

$$VC_1 = VC_0 e^{-K_1 T_{wn}} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

T_{wn} = average waking hours

T_{sn} = average fully restorative sleeping hours

K_1 = complex function of age

$$C_2 \lll C_1$$

As the day progresses, VC_1 gradually reduces until the individual commences sleep.

Figure 2C - "Normal" Circadian Sleep Rhythm

Normal circadian sleep rhythm. Sleep urge is greatest at night with a small increase at mid day. Sleep need increases throughout the waking hours and is replenished during sleep. [Figure Reference: www/mrbarlow.files.wordpress.com]

Figure 2D - Circadian Rhythm Impact on VC_1^*

Illustrative impact of circadian rhythms on VC_1 during waking hours.
* Graph is not to scale.

Figure 2B does not include the impact of one’s daily circadian rhythms (Figure 2C). These rhythms modulate VC_1 during the day as depicted in the Figure 2D.

When sleep occurs, Switch 1 is returned to the “sleep” position and VC_1 is replenished to VC_0 volts per the equation

$$VC_1 = VC_0 e^{-K_1 tw} + K_2 ts \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where tw = number of hours continually awake during the day

ts = number of hours of continuous sleep

K_2 = complex function of age and sleep duration

$$ts \leq VC_0 [1 - e^{-K_1 tw}] / K_2 \quad \quad VC_1 \leq VC_0$$

Figure 2E - *Biphasic Sleep: Midday 30 minute nap

In contrast, consider Figure 2E which reflects a biphasic sleep cycle comprised of an afternoon nap of 30 minutes to augment a night’s sleep. The restorative impact of a short nap is disproportionately large compared to average hourly nighttime rest. The cumulative result is a potential reduction in daily sleep needs. At the onset of a nap, VC_1 should be low enough to ensure sleep latency is no longer than 10 minutes. This does not normally begin to occur until an individual reaches his or her 40’s.

Returning back to Figure 2B, for the average 40 year-old adult who does not nap, (*monophasic sleep*), a “normal” cycle T_w is 16 hours followed by $T_s = 8$ hours of sleep to sustain a non sleep deprived state. For an infant, the normal sleep/wake cycle is significantly shorter. Postulate that a relatively constant amount of energy p is consumed during a “normal” wake cycle T_w hours. This implies that

$$VC_0^2 [1 - e^{-K_1 T_w}] = p \text{ or } T_w = \frac{\ln(1 - p^{2nK_0})}{-2K_1} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

When $VC_0 e^{-K_1 T_w} > V_s$

Correspondingly, for a fully restorative, normal sleep cycle defined as T_s hours, it follows that

$$VC_0 [1 - e^{-K_1 T_w}] = K_2 T_s \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

From equations #4 and #5, with knowledge of K_1 , K_2 and p it is possible to solve for the percentage of daily sleep as a function of age where

$$\% \text{ Daily Sleep} = \left[\frac{T_s}{T_s + T_w} \right]^{100} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Equations #4 and #6 are limited to the case where $VC_1 e^{-K_1 T_w} > .6$

which corresponds to roughly 55 years of age. For ages 55 to 80, T_w and T_s become:

$$T_w = - \left[\frac{\ln .62 - nK_0}{K_1} \right] \dots\dots\dots (7a)$$

$$T_s = e^{-nK_0} \left[\frac{1 - e^{-K_1 T_w}}{K_2} \right] \dots\dots\dots (8a)$$

Equations #4 through #8 yield age-dependent periodic monophasic sleep/wake cycles of varied duration. For a twenty-four hour cycle, the daily sleep and waking cycles, are:

$$T_{sn} = \left[\frac{24 T_s}{T_s + T_w} \right] \dots\dots\dots (7b)$$

$$T_{wn} = 24 - T_{sn} \dots\dots\dots (8b)$$

Figure 2F - Sleep Phases [Quora, Ref 11]

One final qualification on exploring polyphasic sleep strategies using The C Model. Equation #3 suggests it would be possible to totally eliminate a core nightly rest period by taking periodic short naps. Figure 2F shows the various sleep phases for a typical adult. The literature suggests that stage 1 is essential for remembering, learning and problem solving. Deep sleep, associated with stages 3 and 4 diminishes the sleep drive that builds up during the day and is the state when the body releases human growth hormone in pulses. Interruption during deep sleep stops hormone release and leaves one feeling sluggish (*i.e. sleep drunkenness*). It would seem reasonable to speculate that extended deprivation of deep sleep would result in serious health issues. C Model generated results suggest a polyphasic sleep incorporating a minimum core sleep of six (6) hours is desirable.

Returning to Figure 1, during our waking hours what happens when we engage in concentrating on a mental task. This is represented by Switch 2* moving from the “break” position to “concentration.” During the period of concentration (*ta* hours), VC_2 is discharged as shown in *Figure 2G*.

Figure 2G - Concentration/Fully Restorative Break Cycle

* When Switch 2 is initially in the break position, it assumed $VC_2 = VC_1$

$$VC_2 = VC_1 e^{-K_3 ta} \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

$$K_3 = f(n)$$

ta = Time (hours) applied to the mental task

Correspondingly, when the individual takes a break of duration **tb**, **VC₂** is restored per the equation:

$$VC_2 = VC_1 e^{-K_3 ta} + K_4 tb \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

$$K_4 = f(n)$$

$$tb \leq \frac{VC_1 [1 - e^{-K_3 ta}]}{K_4}$$

tb = length of break

$$VC_2 < VC_1$$

In the case of a fully restorative break, **tb** is of duration $\frac{VC_1 [1 - e^{-K_3 ta}]}{K_4}$ as illustrated in Figure 2G.

Per the conceptual C Model, the cognitive ability of the individual normalized to their daily maximum is given by:

Normalized Cognitive Ability

$$\propto \frac{VC_2 - V_{th}}{VC_0 - V_{th}} \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

Correspondingly, the amount of cognitive work done over time **ta** is given by:

Normalized Cognitive Work

$$\propto \int_{tf}^{ta} \frac{VC_2 - V_{th}}{VC_0 - V_{th}} dt \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

tf = mental preparation time preceding cognitive task

Another factor is sleep inertia [SI], a temporary disorientation immediately after awaking from sleep. It has been assumed to be linear where

$$SI = .5/8 \times ts \text{ hours where } ts \text{ is the preceding duration of sleep}$$

Table 1 - *Summary of Model Terms**

n = age of a specific individual in years

ts = specific individual sleep duration

tw = specific individual waking duration

Ts = specific individual monophasic sleep period in a fully restorative sleep/wake cycle

Tw = specific individual waking period in a fully restorative, monophasic sleep/wake cycle

Tsn = sleep period for fully restorative monophasic (i.e., single) sleep period in a 24 hour cycle.

Tw_n = waking period in a 24 hour cycle, $24 - T_{sn}$.

ta = time duration of an applied cognitive task

tb = task break period

p = normalized energy expended during Tw_n ($4 \leq n \leq 55$)

Vs = voltage corresponding to 0 sleep latency

V_{th} = minimum voltage to cognitively function

RoW_{nb} = hourly rate of cognitive work over a defined time period with no interim rest break

RoW_b = hourly rate of cognitive work over time period with one, fully restorative, intermediate break

RoM_b = rate of cognitive work over multiple (b+1) cognitive work periods separated by multiple (b), fully restorative, breaks

SI = sleep inertia, the period of time after waking to establish full cognitive potential

tf = mental preparation time preceding cognitive task

* All time variables expressed in hours.

Summary C Model Equations

The equations for parameters K_0 , K_1 , K_2 , etc. were primarily derived using data from the cited references. In some cases, where data was unavailable, the author drew upon life experience. The methodology was to create equations which yielded a "best fit" to referenced quantitative data and mirrored life experience.

$$\bullet K_0 = .0048 \dots\dots\dots (13)$$

$$V_s = .60$$

$$V_{th} = .15$$

$$\bullet K_1(n) = .0115(.975 + 3.5e^{-(n-1)^4}) \quad n \geq 2 \dots\dots\dots (14)$$

$$\bullet K_2(n, ts)^* = \frac{VC_0[1 - e^{-K_1 Twn}]}{Tsn} \quad (1 - 1.5 \cdot 10^{-6} n^{2.97})^{-35} (1 + e^{-1.5(ts-1.55)}) \dots\dots\dots (15)$$

$$\bullet K_3(n) = .2(1 + 17.5e^{-.25n}) \dots\dots\dots (16)$$

$$\bullet K_4(n) = .73(1 + .04e^{1(n-50)})^{-1} \dots\dots\dots (17)$$

$$p = .213 \dots\dots\dots (18a)$$

$$\bullet \text{Sleep latency} = 2 (VC_1 - 0.6) \text{ hrs} \dots\dots\dots (18b)$$

$$\bullet Tw, Ts \quad 2 \leq n \leq 55 \text{ (monophasic sleep)} \dots\dots\dots (19)$$

$$Twn = \frac{\ln(1 - .213e^{2nK_0})}{-2K_1}$$

$$Tsn = \frac{e^{-nK_0} [1 - e^{-K_1 Twn}]}{K_2}$$

$$\bullet Tw, Ts \quad 55 \leq n \leq 80 \text{ (monophasic sleep)} \dots\dots\dots (20)$$

$$Twn = - \left[\frac{\ln .60 + nK_0}{K_1} \right]$$

$$Tsn = e^{-nK_0} \frac{[1 - e^{-K_1 Twn}]}{K_2}$$

* K_2 is a function of both age (n) and sleep duration (ts), yielding the restorative value of sleep $ts = K_2 \cdot ts$. Twn and Tsn are fixed values associated with the individual in question. For a group of individuals, a reasonable approximation for K_2 is generated by substituting $.0184 = VC_0 [1 - e^{-K_1 Twn}] / Tsn$. Practical application of the equations is illustrated in Table 6, page 43.

- Break/No Break comparison of cognitive rate of work over time period

$(2ta + tb)$

$$R_0 Wb \text{ [single midway break]} = 2 \int_{tf}^{ta} \frac{VC_2 e^{-K_3 t} - .15}{2ta + tb} dt \dots\dots\dots (21)$$

$$R_0 Wnb \text{ [no break]} = \int_{tf}^{2ta + tb} \frac{VC_2 e^{-K_3 t} - .15}{2ta + tb} dt \dots\dots\dots (22)$$

- Rate of cognitive work for multiple (**b**) breaks

$$R_0 Wmb \approx (b+1) \frac{\left[\frac{VC_2}{K_3} [e^{-K_3 tf} - e^{-K_3 ta}] - .15[ta - tf] \right]}{[(b+1)ta + b(tb)]} \dots\dots\dots (23)$$

$R_0 Wmb$ = work rate, multiple breaks, time period (*hours*) $[(b+1)ta + b(tb)]$

b = number of breaks

tf = .033 hours

tb = duration of each fully restorative break (*hours*)

ta = duration of each concentration period (*hours*)

- Cognitive work potential (fluid intelligence) rate of sustainable work vs age

$$\alpha \int_{tf}^{ta} \frac{VC_1 [e^{-K_3 t}] - .15}{ta + tb} dt \dots\dots\dots (24) \qquad tb \approx VC_1 \frac{[1 - e^{-K_3 ta}]}{K_4} *$$

- Deep sleep consideration - daily uninterrupted core sleep > 5 hours

- SI (sleep inertia) = .5/8 ts hours where ts = duration of sleep (hours)

prior to awaking

* results assume $VC_1 = VC_2$

II. C MODEL INTEGRITY

Comparison of C Model Generated Results to Selected Studies

The integrity of The C Model is best measured by comparison to published results encompassing:

- A. Sleep requirements versus age
- B. Continuous and partial sleep deprivation
- C. Sleep debt recovery
- D. Work breaks
- E. Work breaks/napping
- F. Cognitive ability versus age

For comparative purposes, The C Model's results have been normalized to the initial condition of the cited references.

A. Sleep Requirements Versus Age

C Model generated results for ages 3 to 80 years are compared to data from Children's Health, The Merck Manual and The National Sleep Foundation. The C Model range of sleep hours for ages 40 to 80 is derived incorporating monophasic and nap augmented biphasic sleep (Figure 3.0).

Table 2 - [Reference #24] Children's Health (VHi Healthcare)
How Much Sleep Does My Child Need?

Age	Nighttime Sleep	Daytime Sleep	Total Sleep	C Model*
1 year	11 1/4	2 1/2	13 3/4	n/a
1 1/2 years	11 1/4	2 1/4	13 1/2	n/a
2 years	11	2	13	13.6
3 years	10 1/2	1 1/2	12	12.6
4 years	11 1/2	0	11 1/2	11.9
5 years	11	0	11	11.4
6 years	10 3/4	0	10 3/4	11
7 years	10 1/2	0	10 1/2	10.7
8 years	10 1/4	0	10 1/4	10.4
9 years	10	0	10	10.2
10 years	9 3/4	0	9 3/4	10
11 years	9 1/2	0	9 1/2	9.8
12-13 years	9 1/4	0	9 1/4	9.5
14 years	9	0	9	9.4
15 years	8 3/4	0	8 3/4	9.3
16 years	8 1/2	0	8 1/2	9.2

Table 3 - [Reference #16] The Merck Manual 2003. Home Edition. (Merck Research Laboratories, 2003)
Average Daily Sleep Requirements

Age	Total Number of Hours	REM Sleep (percentage of total)	Stage 4 Sleep (percentage of total)	C Model* total number of hours
Newborn	13 to 17	50%	25%	n/a
2 years	9 to 13	30 to 35%	25%	9.8 - 13.6
10 years	10 to 11	25%	25 to 30%	10
16 to 65 years	6 to 9	25%	25%	6.7 - 9.2
Over 65 years	6 to 8	20 to 25%	0 to 10%	7.0 - 8.9

Table 4 - [Reference #18] Sleep Requirements Versus Age
(National Sleep Foundation, 2015)

Age (years)	Sleep Foundation (hours)	C Model* (hours)
1 - 2	11 - 14	n/a
3 - 5	10 - 13	11.4 - 12.6
6 - 13	9 - 10	9.2 - 11.5
14 -17	8 - 10	9.2 - 9.4
18 - 25	7 - 9	8.5 - 9.0
26 - 64	7 - 9	6.7 - 8.5
65 +	7 - 8	7.0 - 8.9

SLEEP DURATION RECOMMENDATIONS

<https://www.sleepfoundation.org/excessive-sleepiness/support/how-much-sleep-do-we-really-need>

Figure 3.0 - Sleep vs. Age - Model Results

- monophasic sleep (no nap)
- - -●- - - biphasic sleep (nap)

"Biphasic or monophasic" indicates either is possible.
 Results exclude impact of circadian rhythms.

B. Continuous and Partial Sleep Deprivation

In a landmark study [1], Colonel Greg Belenky evaluated artillery soldier performance during 72 hours of continuous operations, documenting the decline in performance over time. His work also measured outcomes for troops allowed daily 30 minute naps versus those who remained continuously active. C Model generated results are benchmarked against the study linear regression for no nap and 30 minute nap (Fig. 4). For purposes of illustration, a number of the actual measurements for the no nap case are shown to illustrate the impact of circadian rhythms (Fig. 5). These values are approximate as they were visually extracted from the publication. The circadian rhythms, which vary by individual and age modulate the linear regression values both increasing and decreasing over time. Also included is a comparison of results generated by the U.S. Army's predictive model to C Model results.

In addition, the work by fatigue expert, David Dinges [8], comparing cognitive performance of those continuously awake for 72 hours to those limited to 4 hours of daily sleep is compared to C Model generated results.

Figure 4 - [Reference #1] Degradation in Cognitive Performance in Sleep Deprivation With and Without Daily Nap (30 minutes) (Belenky, 1997)

* Linear regression data extracted from Reference #1

<http://isme.tamu.edu/JSCOPE97/Belenky97/Belenky97.htm>

Figure 5 - [Reference #1] Sleep, Sleep Deprivation and Human Performance in Continuous Operations (Belenky, 1997)

Figure 6 - Comparison of Reference #1 Theoretical Performance vs. The C Model for Partial Sleep Deprivation

Figure 6A - 4 Hours Sleep per Day: Reference vs C Model Comparison

C Model 4 Hours Sleep/Day

N = 25 $K_1 = .0124$ $K_2 = .0753$

Day	Normalized* Rounds per Tube per Day
1	405
2	333
4	237
6	179
8	143
10	122
14	101
20	91

Figure 6B - 5 Hours Sleep per Day: Reference vs C Model Comparison

C Model 5 Hours Sleep/Day

N = 25 $K_1 = .0124$ $K_2 \cdot 5 = .0923$

Day	Normalized* Rounds per Tube per Day
1	385
2	333
4	260
6	214
8	188
10	169
12	159
14	151
20	148

*Rounds per tube per day = 31.9
[16.93VC₁ - 2.85]

Figure 6C - 6 Hours Sleep per Day: Reference vs C Model Comparison

Figure 6D - 7 Hours Sleep per Day: Reference vs C Model Comparison

Reference #8: *The Promise of Sleep (Dement, Vaughn, 1999)*

Extracting from page 231 of the cited reference:

In his latest research, University of Pennsylvania fatigue expert David Dinges restricted the sleep of volunteers over a two week period. Dave concluded that when people sleep only four hours a night for two weeks, their performance scores are the same as those of people who were kept up for three straight days and nights.

To compare this finding versus the C Model projections (*normalized*), cognitive ability is plotted below (*Figure 7*), where results are shown for subjects kept continuously awake versus those sleeping 4 hours per night. After 14 nights, the relative cognitive ability for the four hour sleepers is 27.5% which corresponds to someone continually awake for 75 hours or 3.2 days. The C Model is surprisingly close to Dinges' conclusion.

Figure 7 - C Model Comparison of Absolute Cognitive Potential for No Sleep vs 4 Hours Daily, n = 25 years

C. SLEEP DEBT RECOVERY

In the field of sleep research, sleep debt recovery refers to the amount of additional restorative sleep required after extended periods of wakefulness. One of the most famous cases is that of Randy Gardner, who in a controlled experiment stayed awake for eleven (11) days.

Using data from "The Promise of Sleep," the waking/sleeping recovery data was entered in the C Model to determine if it matched actual observed results.

Reference #8: *The Promise of Sleep (Dement, Vaughn 1999)*

Consider an extreme case of sleep deprivation described in "The Promise of Sleep," by William C. Dement. In 1964, Randy Gardner, a San Diego high school student, stayed up for 264 hours to break the Guinness Book of World Records. Upon completion, Randy went to bed at 6 AM to awake spontaneously at 8:40 PM that evening. After he showered and dressed he stayed up through the night and went to school the next morning. After school he was in bed by 7:30 PM and was roused the next morning at 6 AM. The following day he went to bed at 11 PM and slept until 8 AM Saturday morning. He spent three more nights (*Saturday, Sunday and Monday*) at the Naval Hospital Sleep Laboratory, then one each at one week, six weeks and ten weeks after the marathon. Quoting from the book "judging from the results of his three follow-up nights at the Naval Hospital Sleep Laboratory it appeared that Randy's sleep requirement was a little less than seven hours a day."

The fact that the follow up recording at weeks one, six and ten were almost identical suggests that one week after the marathon, Gardner had replenished his sleep debt. Assuming that he slept an extra hour or two per night on Saturday, Sunday and Monday, it suggests that his Wednesday through Tuesday sleep was in the range of 60 hours versus his normal requirement of less than 41 hours. For a sleep debt of 75 hours (*missed 11 nights of sleep*) Gardiner appeared to require an additional 19 hours to achieve

full restoral from a 75 hour deficit.

How does this compare with the projected recovery using the C Model? His sleep patterns for the period Wednesday through Tuesday were assumed to be:

Wednesday	6:00 AM - 8:40 PM
Thursday	7:30 PM - 6:00 AM (<i>Friday</i>)
Friday	11:00 PM - 8:00 AM (<i>Saturday</i>)
Saturday	11:00 PM - 8:00 AM (<i>Sunday</i>)
Sunday	11:00 PM - 7:00 AM (<i>Monday</i>)
Monday	11:00 PM - 7:00 AM (<i>Tuesday</i>)

Sleep periods Wednesday through Friday are documented results. Saturday though Monday are "guesstimates" assuming Gardner was getting a diminishing amount of extra sleep compared to his "normal" requirement of less than 7 hours. It is also important to note that $K2 = .026$ for Gardner per C Model parameter summary ($n=18 \cdot Ts < 7$).

Figure 8 - Gardner Sleep Map

Referring to Figure 8, based on the sleep patterns VC_1 is shown over the seven day period. The C Model suggests that full restoration would occur by Tuesday 7:00 AM.* Similar results would be generated with varying assumptions of sleep Saturday through Monday night. The bulk of restoration had already been achieved by Saturday morning.

In summary, The C Model seems to align with empirical results, predicting a six (6) day sleep of 59 hours, equating to an additional 18 hours of sleep to achieve full cognitive restoration from a 75 hour sleep deficit. Restoration in this context excludes health related issues such as depression, memory loss, mood swings, etc.

* $VC_0 (n = 18) = .92$, a fully restorative state

D. WORK BREAKS**References #17: *Strategic Rest Breaks Without Reducing Productivity (NIOSH Ergonomics, 2000)***

The study, published in the 2000 edition of *Ergonomics*, a peer-reviewed scientific journal, was carried out by the National Institute of Occupational Safety & Health, a (U.S.) federal work-safety research agency better known by its acronym, NIOSH.

The agency examined the effect of rest breaks on 42 data-entry operators working eight-hour shifts at an Internal Revenue Service office in Austin, Texas. Over a two-month period, the employees alternated their usual schedule with one offering more time away from the PC. In the conventional schedule, they took 15-minute breaks, one mid-morning and the other mid-afternoon. In what researchers called the supplementary schedule, they were allowed four additional five-minute breaks scattered throughout the day. The employees were encouraged to use this time to get up from their work stations and take a short walk or stretch.

Even though employees on the supplementary schedule put in 20 minutes less a day, their productivity remained about the same as when they worked the conventional schedule. Employees with frequent rest breaks typed an average of 8,591 keystrokes per hour, compared with 7,931 for work on a conventional schedule. As a result, the supplementary schedule resulted in only slightly fewer documents produced than did the conventional schedule.

Using The C Model as a reference and assuming;

- The typical workday with no additional breaks are two 1.67 hour work periods with an intervening 15-minute break for the morning and afternoon.
- The four additional 5-minute break further reduce each 1.67 hour work periods into two .77 hour work period with an intervening 5-minute break.

Assuming: $n = 40$, $K_3 = .2$, $K_4 = .719$, $VC_1 = .79$, the amount of work accomplished in a 1.67 work period is given by:

$$W_{nb} = \int_0^{1.67} [VC_1 e^{-K_3 t} - .15] dt = .822$$

The rate of hourly work being done is given by $.822/1.62 = .504$

In contrast, the work accomplished in a 1.67 hour period with the additional 5-minute break is approximated by:

$$W_b = \int_0^{.77} [VC_1 e^{-.2t} - .15] dt + \int_0^{.77} \left[[.79e^{-.2x.77} + \frac{.719}{12}] e^{-.2t} - .15 \right] dt = .829$$

The rate of work at the keyboard is given by $.829/1.54 = .538$

Therefore, if the reported NIOSH speed is 7931 for the normal schedule, the speed with the additional break is given by $(.538/.504) \times 7931 = 8466$ strokes / hour

This compares reasonably well with the measured results of 8,591 strokes per hour. For experienced data entry clerks, tf was assumed to be 0.

E. WORK BREAKS**Reference #22: *A Formula for Perfect Productivity: Work for 52 Minutes, Break for 17 (Thompson, 2014)***

Thompson's article suggests 52 minutes of work followed by a 17-minute break is ideal. Cornell's University Ergonomics Research Laboratory used a program to remind workers to take short breaks. The Cornell project concluded that workers receiving the alerts to take a break were 13% more accurate in their work than coworkers not reminded.

Reference #20: *The Science of Taking Breaks at Work (Seiter, 2014)*

In Seiter's blog post, four alternate algorithms are offered:

1. Pomodoro Method: 25-minutes on, 5-minute break
2. 90-Minute Blocks: 90-minutes on, 20 minutes off
3. 52 - 17 Method: 52-minutes on, 17-minutes off
4. Two 15-minute breaks per day

The article also states that the reason the most productive 10% are able to get the most done during comparatively short periods of working time is that they treat this time as a sprint. They make the most of their "on" time, but then rest up for the next burst. In other words, they work with purpose.

Considering the block of time to be optimized is four (4) hours (*a morning or afternoon*), the productivity potential as a function of the number of breaks is shown for The C Model (Figure 10).

The results indicate somewhere in the range of two (2) to six (6) breaks during this period of duration $T_b = .2T_a$ where T_a is the preceding work period yields optimal results. For example, six (6) breaks corresponds to a case where $7T_a + 6 \times .2 = 4$ hours or $T_a = 30$ minutes, $T_b = 6$ minutes. On the lower end of the scale a minimum of two (2) breaks are required yielding $3T_a + 2 \times .2T_a = 4$ hours or $T_a = 1.17$ hours.

The "52-17 Method," is close to C Model results of 52-15 for 20 year olds. For 40 year olds, the C Model yields 52-10.

"Two 15-minute breaks per day" model, which corresponds to a single morning or afternoon break is clearly non-optimal. The C Model suggests an optimum is achieved working 30 to 70 minutes with corresponding breaks for 6-15 minutes.

Figure 9 - Relative Rate of Work vs Number of Breaks over a 4-Hour Period

F. WORK BREAKS/NAPPING**Reference #7: *The Effects of Napping on Night Shift Performance (Della Rocco, Comperatore, Caldwell, Cruz, 2000)***

This U.S. Department of Transportation (*U.S. DOT*) study was selected as it combines the impact of both breaks and naps on cognitive performance. In this study, sixty Air TRAFFIC Control Specialists (*ATCS's*) were randomly assigned to one of three groups, "No Nap Group (*NN*)," "Short Nap Group (*SN*)," and "Long Nap Group (*LN*)."
ATCS's completed a four day protocol during which they worked three early morning shifts (*0700-1500*) followed by a rapid rotation to the midnight shift (*2300-0700*).
 Subjects completed three 1.5 hour test sessions (*one session before the nap and two sessions after the nap*) during the midnight shift involving the following two computer based tasks, The Air Traffic Scenario Test (*ATST*), and The Bakan, a test of vigilance (*see Table 5*).

Table 5 - Midnight Shift Schedule for Each Nap Condition

Time	No Nap Group	Short Nap Group	Long Nap Group
2300-0030	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST
0030-0100	Break	Break	Break
0100-0130	ATST	ATST	ATST
0130-0145	Break	Break	Break
0145-0300	Break	Break	Nap
0300-0345	Break	Nap	Nap
0345-0520	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST
0520-0530	Break	Break	Break
0530-0700	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST	ATST-Bakan-ATST
0700-1200	Sleep	Sleep	Sleep
1300-1330	ATST	ATST	ATST

The U.S. DOT study's results are compared to those generated by The C Model (*normalized to the number of correct responses in session 1*) for each nap group in Figure 11. The impact of sleep inertia is incorporated in The C Model results.

Figure 10 - Bakan Session Total Correct Responses
 Nap Condition by Session vs Model Results

G. COGNITIVE ABILITY VS AGE

Reference #25: *Cognitive Development (Voelkle, Lindenberger, 2014)*

Results of a study in which 291 people between the ages of six (6) and eighty-nine (89) years were tested using a large collection of tasks to measure fluid intelligence. Crystallized intelligence (*culture/knowledge-based*) evolves differently than fluid intelligence (*biology-based*). The C Model results (*fluid intelligence*) are also shown normalized to a T score = 63 at age 20.

Figure 11 - Fluid Intelligence vs Age

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: *REAL LIFE EXAMPLES*

Given The C Model correlates reasonably well with the cited references, it is interesting to use it to project the impact on cognitive ability for a number of typical life situations. The examples chosen are:

1. Workweek reduced sleep - getting six and one-half (6.5) hours of sleep per night Monday through Thursday
2. Single night sleep deficit - Monday night with a three (3) hour deficit
3. Nighthawks dilemma - a circadian rhythm problem
4. Incorporating a nap to increase productivity - the busy executive
5. Senior sleep dilemma - middle of the night bathroom break
6. Designing school class schedules - the importance of break times
7. Biphasic and polyphasic sleep engineering - searching for ultimate productivity
8. Sleep and education - the impact of school start times on student performance
9. Sleep Loss and Car Crashes - the increased probability of motor accidents associated with sleep deficits
10. Learning and Sleep - the impact of sleep on learning new skills.

Unless otherwise specified, the results are based on a forty (40)-year-old individual requiring eight (8) hours of restorative sleep. This raises the question: Are these results valid for those with significantly different sleep needs, such as individuals who require seven (7) or nine (9) hours? The key factor to consider is the reduction relative to normal sleep requirements. For example, reducing sleep by one and a half (1.5) hours would have a greater impact on someone who normally needs seven (7) hours of sleep compared to someone who needs eight (8) hours. However, the results will be similar if adjusted for different sleep requirements.

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: *REAL LIFE EXAMPLES*

1. WORKWEEK REDUCED SLEEP - *THE IMPACT ON COGNITIVE ABILITY OF A 6.5 HOUR SLEEP ON 40 YEAR-OLD AND AN 18 YEAR-OLD*

Figure 13 compares the impact of cumulative weekday reduced sleep on the normalized cognitive ability of a 40 year-old to that of an 18 year-old. The 40 year-old adult requires eight (8) hours of sleep, but averages only 6 1/2 hours per night Monday through Thursday followed by weekend catch-up sleep. The 18 year-old requires nine (9) hours sleep per night, but averages 6 1/2 hours of sleep on weekdays followed by weekend catch-up sleep.

By Friday, the 40 year-old has a drop in cognitive ability of approximately 16% compared to Monday, whereas the 18 year-old has a 27% drop in the same period. For the week in total, the 40 year-old has a cumulative weekly impact of a 10% reduction in cognitive ability versus a 15% for the 18 year-old.

The C Model demonstrates there is a considerable decline in cognitive ability for both the 40 and 18 year-olds, but more importantly highlights how this decline is magnified for younger people who require more sleep.

Figure 12 - Cumulative Impact of Moderately Reduced Sleep

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: *REAL LIFE EXAMPLES***2. SINGLE NIGHT SLEEP DEFICIT - *MONDAY NIGHT WITH A THREE (3) HOUR SLEEP DEFICIT***

Another example is the case where an adult [$n=40$, $T_{sn} = 8$ hrs] who puts in a long day and only gets five (5) hours sleep Monday night. Figure 14 shows the recovery cycle assuming a return to a "normal" eight (8) hours of sleep per night for the balance of the week. The results speak to the need to recover from a sleep deficit quickly... ideally the next day via a nap or extended night sleep.

Figure 13 - Profile of Sleep Loss Recovery

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: REAL LIFE EXAMPLES

3. NIGHTHAWKS DILEMMA - *A CIRCADIAN RHYTHM PROBLEM*

Consider an example of a 20 year-old college student who is a "nighthawk..." his circadian rhythms peak in the evening. As a result, he can't get to sleep until 1:00 AM or so, and has to get up at 7:00 AM to make early morning classes. As the week progresses he slowly "runs out of gas" until the weekend permits him to catch up on sleep.

Figure 15 shows VC_1 as a function of time during the week. By the time Friday morning comes around, a 33% reduction in cognitive ability has occurred.

One way to counter the reduced cognitive ability and maintain a similar schedule would be to engineer an alternate weekly sleep strategy incorporating a daily nap. Given the student has no idea of his "sleep latency" variations during the day, a good approach is to allocate a total of one hour daily to both fall asleep and nap per the example shown.

Alternate Sleep Schedule

7:00 AM - 5:00 PM Waking Hours

5:00 PM - 6:00 PM Midday Rest After Classes

[20 minute pre-nap / 40 minute nap]

6:00 PM - 1:00 AM Waking Hours

1:00 AM - 7:00 AM Core Sleep

A 20 minute pre-nap interval has been assumed. However, the individual may actually fall asleep earlier or later than the 20 minutes, thus increasing or decreasing his nap interval. Even with variations the restorative impact of the nap remains significant. For example, if the nap is reduced to 30 minutes, the nap restorative impact is only reduced by 10%. The C Model reinforces the notion that even a very short nap provides significant restorative value.

The alternate sleep strategy yields a 10% increase in weekly productivity at the expense of an additional four (4) hours of rest per week. Anecdotally, cognitive ability is incrementally higher during the evening hours, a time generally allocated for homework.

Figure 14 - 20 Year Old Sleep Pattern (*Biphasic vs Monophasic*)

- Biphasic (*with nap*)
- Monophasic (*no nap*)

WITH NAP [BIPHASIC]

VC₁ Tues. AM = .834

VC₁ Wed. AM = $[.834e^{-.01279 \times 10} + .059]e^{-.01279 \times 7} + .111 = .83$

N = 20
 Tsn = 8.8
 K₀ = .0048
 K₁ = .01278
 68 K₂ = .111
 .67 K₂ = .059

NO NAP [MONOPHASIC]				
DAY	VC1 BEGINNING	VC1	VC1	NORMALIZED
	OF DAY	TW = 18 HRS	+ 6 HRS SLEEP	COGNITIVE ABILITY
				BEGINNING OF DAY
Mon.	.91	.723	.834	1.0
Tues.	.834	.662	.713	.9
Wed.	.773	.613	.725	.82
Thurs.	.725	.575	.687	.76
Fri.	.687	.545	.656	.67

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: REAL LIFE EXAMPLES

4. INCORPORATING A NAP TO INCREASE PRODUCTIVITY - *THE BUSY EXECUTIVE*

How about the individual who has no problem sleeping, but wants to get more work done during the day without sleep deprivation?

Take a fifty year old who needs eight hours sleep a night. Their normal daily routine is given in Table 6.1, where work is produced in the morning, afternoon, and the evening in time duration T of 4, 5, and 2 hours respectively. It is assumed that each hour block is comprised of 48 minutes of concentration followed by a 12 minute break. The amount of work is approximated by the integral $\int_0^T .92VC_1e^{-K_1t} - .15 dt$

where VC_1 is the voltage at the beginning of the work session. This approximation is used to avoid lengthy equations associated with a more exact solution.

Table 6.2 presents an alternate daily routine incorporating a midday rest/nap period of 40 minutes comprised of 12 minutes of rest (sleep latency), followed by a 26 minute nap. As one would expect, the nighttime sleep requirement is diminished.

For the driven individual working days and evening, the alternate routine yields a 16% increase without sleep deprivation. For the individual confined to working days, extended evening leisure time becomes available with a 7% improvement.

Table 6.1* - Normal Routine

ACTIVITY	TIME (T)	STARTING VC ₁	WORK OUTPUT
Wake Up	6:00 AM	.786	
AM Work Period	8:00 AM - 12 PM (Noon)	.769	2.16 A
Lunch Break	12 PM - 1:00 PM		
PM Work Period	1:00 PM - 6:00 PM	.726	2.49 A
Evening Work Period	7:00 PM - 9:00 PM		.916 A
Sleep*	10:00 PM - 6:00 AM	.652	
Wake Up	6:00 AM	.786	
TOTAL:			5.57 A

$n = 50, K_2 (ts = .38) = .117, K_2 (ts > 5) = .0173, K_1 = .0115, K_3 = .2$

Table 6.2* - Alternate Routine

ACTIVITY	TIME (T)	STARTING VC ₁	WORK OUTPUT
Wake Up	5:00 AM	.786	
AM Work Period	7:00 AM - 12 PM (Noon)	.769	2.68 A
Lunch Break	12 PM - 1:00 PM		
Rest (Sleep Latency) Nap*	1:00 PM - 1:14 PM 1:14 PM - 1:40 PM	.717	
PM Work Period	1:00 PM - 6:00 PM	.765	2.32 A
Evening Work Period	7:00 PM - 10:00 PM		1.50 A
Sleep*	11:05 PM - 5:00 AM	.687	
Wake Up	5:00 AM	.786	
TOTAL:			6.50 A

$n = 50, K_2 (ts = .38) = .117, K_2 (ts > 5) = .0173, K_1 = .0115, K_3 = .2$

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: *REAL LIFE EXAMPLES*

5. SENIOR SLEEP DILEMMA - *MIDDLE OF THE NIGHT BATHROOM BREAK*

Seniors, like myself, become victims of a shrinking bladder. The result is failure to get a fully restorative nights sleep.

At age 72 I had sleep patterns which I suspected were non optimal. I decided to plug in my current sleep regime to The C Model (*Table 7 - Author's Wake/Sleep Cycle*) to see just how far off the mark I was. I was surprised to see it predicted a fully restorative sleep cycle, i.e. if VC_0 at the beginning of the day = .708 volts, then per The C Model, VC_0 24 hours later is:

$$VC_0(24 \text{ hours later})^* = ((.708e^{-0.114 \times 11.25} + .028)e^{-0.114 \times 4.67} + .061)e^{-0.114 \times 1.5} + .045 = .711$$

In summary, The C Model suggested I would enjoy full restoration with sleep slightly less than $[2.25 + 4.0 + .33]$ 6.55 hours per day.** I wish I had been aware of this when I was younger. I would have "re-engineered" my sleep habits accordingly.

Table 7 - Author's Typical Wake/Sleep Cycle

TIME	PERIOD
6:45 AM - 6:00 PM	Waking Period
6:00 PM - 6:20 PM	Nap (involuntary)
6:20 PM - 11:00 PM	Waking Period
11:00 PM - 3:00 AM	Sleep
3:00 AM - 4:30 AM	Waking Period (reading)
4:30 AM - 6:45 AM	Sleep

The sleep regime presented here is not optimal, but accurately depicted my typical 24 hour day. A better alternative would be an earlier waking time with a nap at midday. Unfortunately, while this nap augmented cycle yields fully restored cognitive ability, the issue of adequate NREM/REM sleep remains an issue. The latter may contribute to decreasing memory ability associated with aging.

* $n = 72$, $VC_0 = .708$, $K_1 = .0114$, $.33K_2 = .028$, $4K_2 = .061$, $2.25K_2 = .045$

** VC_0 cannot exceed 708 volts, therefore slightly less than 6.55 hours is required yielding $VC_0(24 \text{ hours later}) = .708$

III. C MODEL IMPLICATIONS: *REAL LIFE EXAMPLES*

6. DESIGNING SCHOOL CLASS SCHEDULES - *THE IMPORTANCE OF BREAK TIMES*

A method called 4 x 4 block scheduling (Reference #26) splits the academic day for middle and high schoolers into quarters and uses a four period day as shown in the Table 8.

Table 8 - 4x4 Block Scheduling Example

Time	Activity
8:00 - 9:25	Subject #1
9:25 - 9:35	Break
9:35 - 11:00	Subject #2
11:00 - 11:35	Lunch
11:35 - 13:00	Subject #3
13:00 - 13:10	Break
13:10 - 14:50	Subject #4

Block scheduling offers more concentrated experiences of subjects with fewer, usually half as many class transfers.

Using The C Model based on a 15 year-old high school freshman yields cognitive work potential as depicted in Figure 16A.

Figure 15A - Cognitive Potential in a Standard 4x4 Block Schedule

The C Model suggests the 10 minute break is an insufficient refresh time resulting in a 30% reduction in cognitive ability between Subjects #1 and #2. Similar results occur between Subjects #3 and #4. The students opportunity for success is substantially diminished for Subjects #2 and #4.

Table 9 - Model Optimized 4x4 Block Scheduling Example

Time	Activity
8:00 - 9:21	Subject #1
9:21 - 9:39	Break
9:39 - 11:00	Subject #2
11:00 - 11:35	Lunch
11:35 - 12:56	Subject #3
12:56 - 13:14	Break
13:14 - 14:50	Subject #4

Figure 15B - Cognitive Potential in a C Model Optimized 4x4 Block Schedule

Compare these results where each ten minute break is increased to 18 minutes and the overall teaching time is reduced by 16 minutes a day per the schedule in Table 9. The comparative results are plotted in Figure 16B. (Individual class results normalized to .782)

For the conventional 4 x 4 block, the daily cumulative normalized work potential = 3.68 with teaching of 5.91 hours. The 18 minute break 4 x 4 block yielded total work potential of 3.91 (Table 10) with teaching time of 5.35 hours.... an increase in work potential of 6% in 6% less time. Of more importance is the relative balance in cognitive work potential between subjects.

The C Model suggests a relatively small variation in teaching time can have a significant effect on performance potential. For educators it is important to consider these metrics when establishing curricula.

Table 10 - Cognitive Normalized Work Potential

Class	Standard 4X4 Block Schedule Work Potential	Optimized 4X4 Block Schedule Work Potential
Subject #1	1.04	1.0
Subject #2	.73	.94
Subject #3	.95	.95
Subject #4	.68	.84

7. BIPHASIC AND POLYPHASIC SLEEP ENGINEERING - *SEARCHING FOR ULTIMATE PRODUCTIVITY***Reference #23: *How to Stay Productive on a 4 to 6 Hour Sleep Cycle (Torba, 2013)***

Andrew Torba describes two examples of engineering nap strategies to enhance productivity. One of the individuals (*Dubovoy*) switched to polyphasic sleep at age 20. He has a core daily sleep of 3.5 hours supplemented by three 20 minute naps throughout his day. Torba also describes his own daily regimen of 5 hours of core sleep supplemented by a 1-2 hour nap after the normal work day. Using the parameters described in Figure 16, these sleep regimens were tested using The C Model.

Dubovoy

While the idea of multiple short naps is appealing, the individual must have low enough sleep latency to be able to fall asleep within a relatively short time. For example, one would want to fall asleep in less than 5 minutes to secure benefit from a nap period in the order of 20 minutes. What The C Model indicated is that to employ this strategy, you would need to be in a constant state of reduced sleep latency (*i.e. low CV_p*). The bottom line was The C Model indicated that although the "available" hours to work increased by 3.5 - 4.0 hours, the "rate" of output only increased by 11% compared to the "normal," monophasic sleeper.

Torba

In the case of Torba, where he has allocated a 1-2 hour window for his nap, it is not crucial that sleep latency be extremely low. In the analysis, I assumed a 15 minute pre-sleep period followed by a 45 minute nap. The results indicated a potential productivity output in the order of 16% compared to the monophasic approach.

While the strategies seem to offer increased productivity, the C Model results do not address the impact on REM and NREM sleep, both of which are crucial for maintaining good health (*Reference #9*).

Figure 16 - C Model Generated Productivity Comparison

Assumptions

VC ₁ beginning of day:	N = 22	.75 K ₂ = .057	50 min Concentration / 10 min Break
Monophasic = .9	K ₁ = .0125	6.5 K ₂ = .120	Torba: 1 hour; 15 min presleep, 45 min sleep
Dubovoy = .76	K ₃ = .20	VC ₀ = 90	12 min sleep inertia recovery after each nap
Torba = .9	.33 K ₂ = .044		

8. SLEEP AND EDUCATION - *THE IMPACT OF SCHOOL START TIMES ON STUDENT PERFORMANCE*

In Dr. Matthew Walker's book, "Why We Sleep" (Reference #29), he reports:

...almost fifty percent (50%) of public high school students start classes at 7:30

A.M. The school buses begin picking up kids around 5:45 A.M. As a result some children must wake up at 5:15 A.M. or earlier.

A growing number of schools in the US have shifted to an 8:30 A.M start. One outcome was an improvement in academic performance.

In the year of this (*schedule*) change the top performing students improved their combined verbal/math SAT scores 16% from a 1288 to 1500 (*average*).

It is interesting to compare these results to those generated using the C Model. Figure #20 shows the comparative cognitive potential of two groups throughout a week, one starting classes at 7:35 A.M., the other at 8:30 A.M. Results were obtained assuming $n = 17$ with a fully restorative sleep requirement of 8.9 hours.

Although the two groups were only 55 minutes apart in their Sunday through Thursday night sleep, the cumulative differential in cognitive potential is significant at the end of the week. By Friday morning the differential approaches $\frac{92 - .82}{.82} \cdot 100 = 12\%$ If this were a SAT test day, Student Group 2 (*with the later start time*) would have a significant advantage.

Figure #17 - Student Sleep Impact: 8.33 hours vs 7.5 hours

	VC ₁ 6:00 A.M.	VC ₁ 10:30 P.M. BEDTIME	RESTORATIVE SLEEP K ₂ x 7.5	START OF DAY COGNITIVE ABILITY VC ₁ - .15	COGNITIVE ABILITY NORMALIZED TO VC ₀ - .15
SUNDAY	N/A	.753	.138	N/A	N/A
MONDAY	.891	.716	.138	.741	.96
TUESDAY	.854	.687	.138	.704	.91
WEDNESDAY	.824	.663	.138	.674	.88
THURSDAY	.801	.644	.138	.651	.85
FRIDAY	.782	-	-	.632	.82

Student Group # 1 - 7:35 A.M. Start

	VC ₁ 6:50 A.M.	VC ₁ 10:30 P.M. BEDTIME	RESTORATIVE SLEEP K ₂ x 8.33	START OF DAY COGNITIVE ABILITY VC ₁ - .15	COGNITIVE ABILITY NORMALIZED TO VC ₀ - .15
SUNDAY	N/A	.753	.153	N/A	N/A
MONDAY	.906	.737	.153	.756	.98
TUESDAY	.890	.724	.153	.74	.96
WEDNESDAY	.877	.713	.153	.727	.94
THURSDAY	.867	.705	.153	.717	.93
FRIDAY	.859	-	-	.709	.92

Student Group # 2 - 8:30 A.M. Start

$$n = 17 \quad K_1 = .0132 \quad K_2 = .0184 \quad VC_0 = .92 \quad T_{sn} = 8.9 \text{ hrs}$$

9. SLEEP LOSS AND CAR CRASHES - *THE INCREASED PROBABILITY OF MOTOR ACCIDENTS ASSOCIATED WITH SLEEP DEFICITS*

In his book, "Why We Sleep" (Reference #29), Dr. Matthew Walker references the 2016 AAA Foundation study of 7000 drivers which reveals how catastrophic drowsy driving is when it comes to car crashes. Figure #21 summarizes the AAA Foundation study results compared to results using the C Model.

The C Model results assumed that individuals with differing sleep times all went to bed at 12:00 A.M. and their state of sleep latency was compared at 7:00 P.M. later that evening. It was assumed that the increase in accidents was proportional to the ratio of 8 hr sleeper sleep latency / actual sleep latency. Results were derived based on $n = 40$, $K_1 = .01174$, $.018 \leq K_2 \leq .020$, sleep latency = 2 (VC₁ - .6) hrs, VC₁ = .683 prior to sleep.

The C Model results did not include the impact of circadian rhythms, which can vary significantly by individual. What is significant is that even after a single night of abbreviated sleep can result in a condition of zero sleep latency, a dangerous condition when driving.

Figure #18 - Increased Accident Risk Comparison (from 2016 AAA Foundation Study)

Hours of Sleep	Ref 29	C Model Derived
< 4 Hrs.	11.5	8.7
4 - 5 Hrs.	4.3	3.05
5 -6 Hrs.	1.9	1.9
6 -7 Hrs.	1.3	1.4
8 Hrs.	-	1.0

10. LEARNING AND SLEEP - *THE IMPACT OF SLEEP ON LEARNING NEW SKILLS.*

In his book *Why We Sleep* (Reference #29), Dr. Matthew Walker describes an experiment in which he took a group of right-handed pianists and had them learn a new left-hand piano sequence. He divided them into two groups, both taught the same left-handed technique. The first group learned in the morning and was tested 12 hours later. The second group learned in the evening and was tested the following morning, after a fully restorative night of sleep. The second group showed a 20% improvement in speed and nearly a 35% improvement in accuracy compared to Group 1. After a full night's sleep, Group 1 also showed a comparable increase in performance.

Assuming that the average age of the participants $n = 20$, the respective C Model cognitive ability of the groups are shown below. The timing of learning and testing are assumptions.

Group #1: Learning 8:00 A.M., testing 8:00 P.M. - same day

Group #2: Learning 8:00 P.M., testing 8:00 A.M. - next day

C Model cognitive ability at testing time,

$$\text{Group \#1: } e^{-K_0x^{20}} \times e^{-K_1x^{12}} - .15 = .592$$

$$\text{Group \#2: } e^{-K_0x^{20}} - .15 = .715$$

$$\text{Group \#2 relative \% advantage} = \frac{.715 - .592}{.592} = 21\%$$

Although the C Model cannot differentiate between speed and accuracy, it is interesting that the measured speed differential of 20% coincides with the 21% C model cognitive advantage.

IV. CONCLUSIONS / NEXT STEPS

A mathematical model (C Model) has been developed to quantify how sleep patterns and workday dynamics influence cognitive ability, normalized to an individuals' maximum daily potential. Sleep in this context includes both the core night rest and midday napping.

Initial validation was performed by comparing model behavior with findings from a broad range of studies including those on sleep deprivation, sleep recovery, sleep engineering, napping, age dependent sleep need, workday/classroom breaks, and fluid intelligence capability as a function of age. The C Model was then applied to a number of common sleep and workday scenarios to evaluate impact and where applicable, suggest corrective measures.

The C Model does not incorporate algorithms addressing REM and NREM sleep requirements... factors strongly tied to mood, memory, depression, and immunity. Instead, in addition to nap augmentation, it is assumed a minimum daily core sleep ≥ 6 hours is required for an adult. Circadian rhythms were also excluded as their substantial variability across individuals and their age make a single formulation impossible. Circadian patterns significantly influence timing of night time sleep and midday restorative naps. A common example of the latter is the drowsiness many people experience shortly after lunch, where a brief nap "break" of about 30 minutes can deliver a disproportionately large positive impact, conditional on a sleep latency being less than 10 to 15 minutes.

An interesting set of empirical observations on sleep and work breaks are contained in Lehnardt's "45 Interesting Facts About Napping" (Lehnardt, 2016):

- » “Most Europeans, except the Germans usually snooze or relax in the middle of the day. China, India and parts of the Middle East are also napping territories.”

- » “Sleeping experts recommend keeping afternoon naps to fewer than 1.5 hours to avoid interfering with nighttime sleep. For most people, a snooze of 15 to 30 minutes is best”
- » “To counter grogginess, sleep researchers suggest keeping naps to 20 minutes or less. Longer naps can create a sleep “hangover” or sleep inertia and affect nighttime sleep.”
- » “Over 85 % of mammals are polyphasic sleepers, which means they sleep for short periods throughout the day. Humans are unusual in that they have two distinct periods of the day: sleep and wakefulness. Scientists are unclear if this bifurcation of the day is an artificial sleep pattern, or if breaking sleep into several naps over a 24 hour period is more natural.”
- » “Those who relish naps are in good company: JFK, Ronald Reagan, Napoleon, Albert Einstein, Thomas Edison and George A Bush all savored an afternoon nap.”
- » “A NASA study on military sleepy pilots and astronauts found a 40 minute nap improved performance by 34 % and alertness by 100 %.”
- » “Even catnaps of 6 minutes (not counting the 5 minutes it takes to fall asleep on average) make a difference in how well people retain information.”
- » “Since Thomas Edison invented the light bulb in 1879, nighttime sleep for the average American has dropped from nine hours per night to less than seven.”
- » “While research shows that napping has important health benefits, napping is still associated with several false stigmas in the U.S., including laziness, lack of ambition, low standards, or an activity exclusively reserved for children, the sick, and elderly.”

- » "U.S. companies are incorporating facilities in the workplace. According to the National Sleep Foundation, 16 % of those surveyed said their employers allowed a nap.”
- » “ Cornell’s University Ergonomics Research Laboratory used a program to remind workers to take a short breaks. The project (ref 20) concluded that workers receiving the alerts to take a break were 13 % more accurate in their work than workers not reminded.”

For the non technical reader, who experiences conditions similar to any of the examples in Section III, it is my hope this paper will provide insight and offer individuals a pathway to optimizing their cognitive potential.

Looking forward, a logical step would be to have a recognized sleep lab validate/optimize the C Model, the objective being to define and publish the cognitive "price" one pays for poor sleep management.

I also suspect that further insight will be realized in the study of naps and their impact on memory and the associated REM/NREM implications. My personal experience is that my midday short naps were followed by increased clarity, memory recall, and a substantial boost in duration time for "high concentration" cognitive work.

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